

Refractory Cutaneous Sarcoidosis without Pulmonary Involvement: A Case Report and Review of Literature

Ghada E. Esheba ^{*1,2}

1. Pathology, Umm Alqura University, Makkah, KSA
2. Pathology, Tanta University, Tanta, Egypt

***Correspondence to:** Ghada E. Esheba, geesheba@uqu.edu.sa

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Abstract

Extrapulmonary sarcoidosis is rare. Cutaneous involvement is the most common extrapulmonary presentation. Cutaneous sarcoidosis is a challenging disease due to its diversity and resemblance to various skin diseases. We present here a case of cutaneous sarcoidosis without pulmonary involvement. A 47-year-old woman presented with red papules on the face one year ago and she was diagnosed as a case of acne vulgaris, however, the skin lesions were resistant to treatment. The patient then developed similar papules on nose, arms, and chest. Skin biopsy showed non-caseating granulomas and systemic workup for sarcoidosis was positive. The patient was eventually diagnosed with sarcoidosis and treated by mometasone furoate 0.1% cream and tacrolimus. The skin lesions resolved completely after two months of treatment. This case report spots the light on the importance of considering sarcoidosis in the differential diagnosis of any refractory skin lesions and underscore the significance of early identification of skin manifestations of sarcoidosis, which may predict the development of systemic disease.

Keywords: *non-caseating granulomas, angiotensin converting enzyme, interleukin-2, cutaneous sarcoidosis, extrapulmonary sarcoidosis, sarcoidosis.*

Introduction

Sarcoidosis is a multi-systemic disease with worldwide distribution. It is characterized by the presence of non-caseating epithelioid granulomas, the latter can be found in any organ, however, the lung is the most common organ involved followed by bilateral hilar lymphadenopathy [1].

Sarcoidosis was first described in 1875 by Jonathan Hutchinson and it was more of a dermatological oddity. Since then, more researches were performed and sarcoidosis gradually evolved into a multi-systemic disease [2].

The etiology and pathogenesis of sarcoidosis is poorly understood and it is thought to be the result of immune dysregulation and an environmental trigger, such as infection and toxins in a genetically predisposed

individual. The granulomatous inflammation may be due to an overwhelming cell-mediated immune reaction to an unidentified antigen [3].

Sarcoidosis has variable clinical presentations according to the affected organ. Most patients suffer from respiratory tract involvement with the most common presentations are shortness of breath, dry cough, chest pain, and wheezing [2]. Skin, eyes, liver, spleen, joints, and peripheral lymph nodes are affected in 10% to 30% of cases. Cardiac and neurological manifestations are uncommon; however, they can be fatal [4-6].

Extrapulmonary sarcoidosis usually affects females below 40 years of age. Cutaneous sarcoidosis (CS) is the most common extrapulmonary presentations, and it may be the only clinical manifestation in the patient [5].

CS varies markedly in morphology, hence the name "great imitator". It may present with single or multiple red, skin-colored or violaceous macules, papules, plaques or nodules, therefore, the diagnosis can be very challenging and often requires clinicopathological and radiographic correlation and laboratory workup as well [7].

CS is classified based on the presence of non-caseating granulomas into: specific lesions which have noncaseating granulomas in skin biopsies and non-specific lesions which do not have such granulomas. The former includes: macules papules, plaques, subcutaneous nodules, lupus pernio (LP), infiltrative scars, and other rare forms such as ulcerative sarcoidosis, nail, scalp, and mucosal sarcoidosis [2,7].

Erythema nodosum is the most common form of the non-specific lesions. Macules, papules, subcutaneous nodules and erythema nodosum have a better prognosis than plaques and LP [8].

Cutaneous sarcoidosis rarely causes significant morbidity or mortality per se; however, the disease may have a significant psychosocial effect due to its disfiguring nature. The degree of systemic involvement defines the treatment and prognosis of CS [2].

Although there is no specific treatment for sarcoidosis, systemic corticosteroids remain the standard of care for individuals with severe clinical presentation, progressive pulmonary disease or extensive extrapulmonary manifestations. Immunomodulators may be used in some cases [9].

Managing skin lesions of sarcoidosis can be very challenging. Asymptomatic lesions usually resolve spontaneously without therapy and require just observation. On the other hand, disfiguring and widespread skin lesions are often associated with extensive systemic manifestations and require treatment [5].

Treatment options for skin lesions include: Intralesional triamcinolone injections, high-potency topical

corticosteroids, tacrolimus in refractory cases, and topical retinoids. Systemic corticosteroids may be prescribed for patients with widespread, extensive or refractory skin lesions. In addition, systemic immunomodulatory therapies such as chloroquine and tetracyclines, systemic immunosuppressive treatments such as methotrexate, leflunomide, azathioprine, and biologicals such as tumor necrosis factor antagonists may be also used [1,5,10].

Case Presentation

A 47-year-old woman presented with red papules on the face for one year (Figure 1) which was treated as an acne vulgaris with no improvement. The patient then developed similar papules on nose, arms, and chest.

FIGURE 1: Multiple red papules on the face.

Laboratory investigations were done and revealed elevated levels of : C-reactive protein (CRP) (13 mg/dl, normal range is 0.8-1.0 mg/dL), erythrocytes sedimentation rate (ESR) (34 mm, normal range is less than 20 mm/hr), serum angiotensin-converting enzyme (ACE) level (114 IU/mL, normal range: 20-95 IU/mL), interleukin-2 (IL-2) (1080.45 pg/mL; reference range: 175.3-858.2 pg/mL), IL-6 (24.26 pg/mL, normal range is up to 7 pg/mL). Total serum calcium was slightly elevated (11.4 mg/dL, normal range is 8.1-10.4

mg/dL).

Chest x-ray was unremarkable and both lung fields were clear. Lung function tests were normal. Renal function tests were performed to exclude renal sarcoidosis due to the presence of hypercalcemia and they were normal.

Multiple punch biopsies were taken from the papules on the face and arms and revealed the presence of naked non-caseating epithelioid cell granulomas with giant cells. The majority of these granulomas had no peripheral mononuclear inflammatory infiltrate (Figure 2) and (Figure 3), while rare granulomas have very thin rim of lymphocytes.

FIGURE 2: Skin biopsy showing multiple dermal granulomas (H & E ×40).

FIGURE 3: Higher power view showing “naked” non-caseating granulomas with epithelioid cells, macrophages and giant cells (H & E $\times 200$).

Two types of giant cells were seen within the granulomas; Langhans-type with an arch-shaped arrangement of nuclei at the periphery of the cell and a foreign body-type with random distribution of nuclei (Figure 4).

FIGURE 4: Two non-caseating granulomas showing Langhans giant cells (asterisk) and foreign-body type giant cells (arrow head) (H & E $\times 200$).

The giant cells had star-like intracytoplasmic asteroid bodies (Figure 5) and Schaumann bodies which are round calcified protein inclusions within the cells. No evidence of organisms on culture or staining was detected.

FIGURE 5: Giant cell containing star-like intracytoplasmic asteroid bodies (asterisk) (H & E $\times 400$).

Histopathological and laboratory findings were consistent with sarcoidosis. The patient was treated by mometasone furoate 0.1% cream, 30 g twice daily for two weeks then two times/week for two months and tacrolimus 0.1% ointment once a day twice weekly. The cutaneous papules started to fade gradually after one month and resolved completely after two months of the treatment course with no subsequent relapse. The patient is followed up by a regular chest x-ray that showed no involvement of both lungs.

Discussion

Sarcoidosis is a diagnosis of exclusion due to its markedly variable clinical presentation and multi-systemic involvement and it is a diagnostic challenge to all physicians [11].

Diagnosis depends on a compatible clinical and radiological picture, the presence of non-caseating granuloma in a biopsy from affected site and the exclusion of other mimics such as lymphoproliferative disorders, Hodgkin's lymphoma and other causes of granulomatous inflammation such as leishmaniasis, toxoplasmosis, leprosy and tuberculosis (lupus vulgaris) [11].

Tuberculous granulomas are commonly caseating, surrounded by lymphocytic cuff and usually found in the upper dermis, in contrast to sarcoidosis granulomas which are naked and uniformly distributed in the dermis. Granulomas in leprosy are present mainly around dermal nerves [1,12].

Cutaneous lesions can appear before, during, or after systemic involvement. Biopsy from skin lesions is more accessible and less invasive than biopsy from the lung or other visceral organs. Therefore, identifying skin lesions can help in early diagnosis and prognosis of the systemic disease [2,7].

It was shown that almost 25 % of patients had CS before the development of systemic manifestations and the prevalence of systemic involvement in CS varies from 29-90%. Female sex, younger age (<54 years), high levels of ACE, IL-2R and CRP were significantly associated with systemic manifestation [1].

In our patient, a comprehensive history taking and complete physical examination were conducted to detect the presence of extra-cutaneous disease. The patient performed chest x-ray and pulmonary function tests to exclude respiratory disease and no extra-cutaneous disease could be identified.

In consistence with our case, Hassan et al, reported a case of cutaneous sarcoidosis without lung involvement, however and in contrast to our patient, the ACE level in their case was normal [13].

Boch et al in their cohort study, found that 38% of patients had an isolated cutaneous disease, while 62% of patients developed a multi-systemic disease during follow-up [1].

Similarly, Mahabal et al reported that six patients had isolated cutaneous sarcoidosis without systemic disease [12].

Laboratory tests in the current patient revealed elevated levels of CRP, ESR, serum ACE, IL-2, and IL-6, and slightly elevated total serum calcium. ACE is a marker of sarcoid activity; it is produced in the epithelioid cells of the sarcoid granuloma under the stimulation of T-cells and its level is elevated in about 60-80% of patients. However, it is not sensitive nor specific to sarcoidosis [11].

IL-2 is a recent biomarker and is more sensitive and superior to ACE for diagnosing sarcoidosis. Elevated IL2 level was reported to be significantly associated with systemic involvement and low IL-2R levels were detected in patients without pulmonary disease [1,14].

In our case, the patient had an elevated ACE level, however, no systemic involvement has been detected. Furthermore, the IL-2 level was not that much high compared to other reports on CS with systemic involvements [1,2,11,14].

Therefore, our patient was kept in a regular follow-up with clinical and radiological monitoring, as she may develop systemic manifestations later on during the course of the disease.

Microscopic examination of skin biopsy from the current case revealed the presence of classical naked granuloma, a finding consistent with that of existing literature which documented that naked granuloma is pathognomonic for sarcoidosis [15,16].

On the other hand, Mahabal et al., found naked granulomas in only 55.3% of cases in their series, while the remaining 44.7% of cases exhibited non-naked granulomas. Moreover, the authors detected perineural localization of granulomas in one of their cases, a finding which necessitated them to exclude leprosy [12].

Of note, our patient has mildly elevated serum calcium. Hypercalcemia in sarcoidosis may indicate renal or rarely bone marrow involvement [11]. However, our patient did not suffer from renal or bone marrow sarcoidosis.

Conclusions

In conclusion, this case report casts the light on the value of early identification of cutaneous manifestations of sarcoidosis, which may predict the presence of systemic disease. Recognizing the different manifestations of CS can help early diagnosis.

Patients with sarcoidosis limited only to skin should be regularly followed up to check disease activity and to detect early systemic involvement regardless of the extent of cutaneous involvement.

Disclosures

Consent was obtained by all participants in this study. The Biomedical Research Ethics Committee Umm Al-Qura University issued approval HAPO-02-K-012-2023-11-1867. Written informed consent was obtained from the patient for publication of this case report and accompanying images. A copy of the written consent is available for review by the editor-in-chief of this journal on request. Conflicts of interest: No Conflicts of interest have been declared.

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